

Applications of differentiated CAD kernel in gradient-based aerodynamic shape optimization

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This work uses the algorithmically differentiated (AD) version of the the open-source Computer Aided Design (CAD) library Open CASCADE Technology (OCCT) to compute geometric derivatives. Here the differentiated OCCT is applied to two different gradient-based shape optimisation test-cases. First, the differentiated OCCT is utilised to develop a gradient-based re-parametrisation tool that fits a B-spline surface to an optimised mesh of a duct used in an automotive application. This step is performed in CAD-free shape optimisation context in order to find a parametric model that approximates the optimised mesh. Second, the differentiated OCCT is coupled with an adjoint CFD solver to run a CAD-based shape optimisation of a compressor stator blade.

I. Introduction

Aerodynamic shape optimisation methods are progressively affirming their importance in industrial design. These methods can be used to improve the performance of crucial aero-engine components such as compressor/turbine blades and industrial channels. In particular, for gradient-based optimisations, the adjoint method^{1,2} is extensively used. It allows to evaluate the sensitivities of a scalar objective with respect to an arbitrary number of control variables in a single computation.

In shape optimisation, we also need the derivative of the shape parametrisation to complete the chain rule of derivatives. A wide range of parametrisations have been developed, which can be categorised into CAD-free and CAD-based methods. CAD-free methods³ also often referred as mesh- or lattice-based, optimise the positions of computational grid points using either a globally interpolated distortion field from radial basis functions (RBF), an auxiliary grid defining perturbations such as Free-Form deformation (FFD) or lattices of Hicks-Henne bumps. Mesh-based approaches use the surface mesh of the CFD grid⁴ to impose a displacement. The design space of mesh-based methods is actually very rich for the CFD computation, high-frequency oscillations are not damped adequately, and hence require regularisation.

A major drawback of all CAD-free methods is that the optimised shape exists only as a mesh. Indeed, in industry it is common practice to maintain a master CAD model which is used by many design and analysis processes. Furthermore, in complex system design this datum geometry enables cross discipline, multi-physics design, essential for advanced design. Importing the shape back to CAD after a numerical optimisation step is an open challenge and could incur significant approximation errors which impair the quality of the optimum.

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Alternatively, CAD-based methods work with the CAD system in the design loop and use CAD parameters as the design variables. The main advantage is that a baseline CAD geometry is taken as an input and an optimised CAD geometry is produced as an output. However, in the context of gradient-based optimisation, these methods require the calculation of the derivative of a surface displacement w.r.t. perturbation of a CAD design variable, the *shape sensitivity*. Their evaluation is not straightforward and several authors have approached this problem with different techniques.

Robinson et al.⁵ apply finite-differencing to commercial CAD system to compute these derivatives. Unfortunately, there are several limitations to this approach. Firstly, the shape sensitivities are affected by truncation or round-off error if the size of the design variable is not appropriately chosen. Secondly, to avoid issues with topology changes of patch net and patch renumbering, the geometry is projected onto an STL approximation and displacements are computed between a point on the original surface and its projection on the STL. This projection may be erroneous in regions of high curvature. Given sufficiently accurate differences however, this approach allows to include into the CAD-based optimisation loop a wide range of CAD algorithms including explicit parametrisation with embedded geometrical constraints.

Dannenhoffer and Haines⁶ use the open-source CAD-kernel Open CASCADE Technology (OCCT). To compute the shape derivatives, they apply analytic differentiation to known simple shapes such as circles or cylinders defined by origins, radii and axes. For more complex geometries and geometrical algorithms, the derivatives are evaluated using finite differences.

To avoid truncation errors or the need for surface projection, one can use the algorithmic/automatic differentiation (AD) technique if the CAD sources are available. This technique automatically computes the derivatives of functions defined by computer programs. To apply it to a certain program, one integrates an AD software tool into its sources. One of such AD software tools named ADOL-C (*Automatic Differentiation by Overloading in C++*) is developed at the University of Paderborn. We used it to differentiate the OCCT kernel to compute the geometric derivatives.⁷ As opposed to finite differences, these geometric derivatives are exact (up to floating point round off). Furthermore, the computational efficiency of the method is superior to the finite difference approach, as demonstrated also in our previous study.⁷

Another requirement for CAD-based shape optimisation workflow is to define the parametrisation of the test-case. Indeed, the parameters that control the CAD model have to be carefully chosen. Nowadays CAD systems usually provide some very intuitive and user-friendly parameters that allow the user to generate and control the CAD model, e.g. for pipes, the typical parameters are the radius of the circular section and the length of the pipe. Unfortunately, the design space provided by this type of parametrisation is very poor and not suitable for shape optimisation. In fact, a change in these parameters would generate a CAD model that although different would be still close to the previous one. To use an appropriate parametrised baseline geometry, we need to find the best approximation of the parametric model to a given shape. This result can be achieved effectively using gradient-based methods, as will be shown in section III.

The paper consists of four sections. The section II gives an introduction to the algorithmic differentiation of the OCCT kernel. The section III explains how the *differentiated OCCT* can be used to develop a re-parametrisation tool and its application to an automotive channel. The section IV describes the application of the differentiated OCCT library to the CAD-based optimisation workflow. The section V summarises the results obtained in this work.

II. Algorithmic Differentiation of the OCCT CAD-Kernel

Algorithmic differentiation (AD) is a technique to compute derivatives of functions defined by computer programs. Any computer program, no matter how complicated, executes a sequence of elementary arithmetic operations (+, −, *, /) and elementary functions (exp, log, sin, cos etc.). Applying the chain rule to these operations, one can compute derivatives of an arbitrary order accurately to the machine precision. In principle, AD exploits this fact and augments these operators/functions with additional statements to compute the derivatives. This introduces the *operator overloading* concept that is present in many AD tools nowadays. One of such mature open-source AD tools is ADOL-C and we used it to differentiate OCCT sources.

ADOL-C⁸ (*Automatic Differentiation by Overloading in C++*) uses the *operator overloading* concept to compute first and higher order derivatives of vector functions that are defined by computer programs written in C/C++. It defines the `adouble` class that overloads the most common operators used in C/C++ and implements additional derivative statements. To integrate it into a certain source-code, one replaces the

declaration types of all relevant *real* variables (e.g. `float`, `double`) with the `adouble` type.

Furthermore, ADOL-C provides two different implementations of the *adouble* class, based on differentiation modes, i.e. ways of derivative computation:

- *traceless* (differentiation mode: forward),
- *trace-based* (differentiation modes: forward and reverse).

The *traceless forward* mode computes the derivatives on-the-fly together with the primal/function evaluation. It is simpler to understand because every operator contains both primal and derivative code in its implementation. More advanced features are available in the *trace-based* options. There the operator overloading first generates an internal representation of the function to be differentiated – called *trace*. After the *trace* is generated, one calls the ADOL-C drivers to compute the derivatives. They provide a possibility to compute the derivatives using the reverse mode of AD that can dramatically reduce the temporal complexity of the derivative computation. Both *traceless* and *trace-based* options can compute the derivatives in one direction (*scalar* mode) or many directions (*vector* mode).

All ADOL-C differentiation options were integrated into the OCCT sources. The differentiation process was not straightforward and it involved a significant amount of code modification, as we had to deal with a lot of compile-time and run-time issues that are explained in our previous study.⁷ Here we are going to give an example how to use the differentiated OCCT sources to compute geometric derivatives with the *traceless* forward vector mode, as it is easier to use than the *trace-based* versions.

A *traceless adouble* class, defined in `adt1` namespace (header `adt1.h`), consists of two properties: (i) one *double*-type variable for storing the *primal* and (ii) one *double*-type array (pointer) for storing the derivatives, named *adval*. The *adval* array has p elements, where p is a number of directions. By default, this value is set to 1, which implies that the *scalar* mode is being used. In case the *vector* mode is being used ($p > 1$), the i -th element of the *adval* array (in every *adouble* object) corresponds to the i -th direction, where $i = 0, \dots, p - 1$. In other words, each design parameter (independent variable) has its own dedicated derivative element in the *adval* array. This enables simultaneous gradient computation w.r.t. many design parameters, i.e. with a single program execution.

There are two possibilities to set the number of directions – p . Simpler option is to call the method `adt1::setNumDir(p)` just at the beginning of the `main` function. Here is important that the *setNumDir* method is executed before any *adouble* object initialisation, otherwise a run-time memory exception might occur. Another option is to change it directly in the ADOL-C sources (file `adouble_t1.cpp`). This is the safer way to do it, but requires re-compilation of the ADOL-C sources. With the differentiated OCCT, we have to set the number of directions in the ADOL-C sources. The reason is that OCCT uses static variables and the static variables (in C++) are initialised before the `main` function even starts. Then a call to `adt1::setNumDir(p)` will corrupt the memory allocation of those variables. Therefore, to avoid any run-time exception with differentiated OCCT, we chose the safer option of changing the number of directions.

To set and get the derivative value of an *adouble* object, one uses the methods *setADValue* and *getADValue*, respectively. Likewise, the methods *setValue* and *getValue* are used to set and get the *primal* part. These values can be also set via *adouble* constructor or assignment operator – more details can be found in the ADOL-C manual that is provided together with the sources.

In order to explain how to use the differentiated OCCT kernel with the *traceless* forward mode of ADOL-C, we have created an example shown in Listing1. Let's consider a parametrisation with n design parameters defined as a vector of *adoubles*. To set their *primal* values, one can simply use the assignment operator (`=`), as shown in the line no. 3. The next step is to set the AD values of each design parameter. Here the number of directions p is set to be equal to n , such that every design parameter has its own column (element) in the *adval* array. To insert a derivative seed in an *adouble* object, one uses the method `setADValue(index, seed)`, as shown in the line no. 5. Therefore, the i -th design parameter will have the i -th *adval* column activated with value 1, while other values will remain 0. To explain this in different words, each design parameter's *adval* array will correspond to a different row in the identity matrix of size n . Having such seeded *adouble* objects, one proceeds with the geometry construction and ADOL-C takes care of propagating those seeds through the whole computation process. In this example we are constructing a B-spline surface (class *Geom_BSplineSurface*), as shown in line no. 7. The B-spline surface class provides the method *D0* to evaluate a 3-D point in a given (u, v) parametric coordinates pair, as shown in line no. 13. Here for example, we are computing a point with the parametric coordinates $(0.2, 0.3)$. After the point is computed, the derivatives in (X, Y, Z) coordinates are extracted with the `getADValue(index)`

method as shown in the lines no. 16, 17 and 18, where the *index* corresponds to the *i*-th design parameter. Therefore, the order of seeding the design parameters is the same as the order of extracting the derivative values. This small example in principle demonstrates how the *traceless* forward mode should be used with the differentiated OCCT sources to compute the surface point derivatives w.r.t. design parameters.

Listing 1. Traceless forward mode with OCCT (simplified)

```

1 vector<adouble> designParameters(n);
2 //initialise the design parameters, e.g. with dummy values:
3 for(int i = 0; i < n; ++i) designParameter[i] = i + 1.;
4 //put the derivative seeds
5 for(int i = 0; i < n; ++i) designParameters[i].setADValue(i, 1.);
6 //construct the geometry
7 Handle(Geom_BSplineSurface) bSurface = ConstructGeometry(designParameters);
8 //extract the surface point derivatives w.r.t. all design parameters
9 vector<double> cadDerivatives;
10 adouble u = 0.2;
11 adouble v = 0.3;
12 gp_Pnt aPnt;
13 bSurface->D0(u, v, aPnt);
14 for(int i = 0; i < n; ++i)
15 {
16     cadDerivatives.push_back(aPnt.X().getADValue(i));
17     cadDerivatives.push_back(aPnt.Y().getADValue(i));
18     cadDerivatives.push_back(aPnt.Z().getADValue(i));
19 }

```

The previously described code can be adapted to compute the derivatives in all mesh points – the so-called CAD sensitivities. Before using them in an optimisation workflow, we have verified their correctness against central scheme finite differences (FD). A qualitative comparison of AD and FD w.r.t. one camber-line design parameter of the TU Berlin stator blade is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. CAD sensitivities evaluated by AD (left) and FD (right)

III. Application 1: Re-parametrisation tool

While a CAD description of the geometry forms the backbone of engineering design and analysis, most often the CAD geometry is not equipped with a shape parametrisation, or the parametrisation is arising from a particular design workflow and does not offer design variables that are suitable for optimisation. Typically the first step will be to develop a suitable parametrisation and to then fit those parameters to best approximate the baseline shape. Since the fit is to a baseline shape, which will be altered by the design optimisation, an exact fit is not desired, nor is it achievable. However, care must be taken to replicate the design intent, e.g. in the design of turbomachinery blades, the local streamwise curvature of the blade is very closely related to the pressure gradient, which in turn determines the pressure profile along the blade. It may hence be much more important to match local curvature than surface location. As will be shown in this section, the gradients provided by the differentiated CAD kernel can be used to design a very flexible best fit system.

A fitting algorithm of a parametrised surface to given data points, either arising from a different, static CAD model or from some surface sampling procedure, will be demonstrated for the example of an automotive climate duct. To develop such an algorithm is a challenging task. In particular, the fitting algorithm has to fulfill two requirements. One is to reproduce all local shape features that effectively affect the objective function during the flow optimisation. The other requirement is to clean the optimised mesh from the local mesh surface noise.

The re-parametrisation tool consists of two parts: (i) mesh preprocessing done by CAD tools, that results in a B-spline surface that approximates the mesh, (ii) B-spline surface fitting to the mesh by using

the derivative information from the differentiated OCCT kernel.

We investigate here the the *s-bend* duct - an automotive test-case proposed by VW (Fig. 2).

A. Mesh Preprocessing

The proposed re-parametrisation technique is developed for 'tube-like' topology ducts, as shown in Fig. 2. The extension of this technique to 'manifold-like' connections (characterised by bifurcation) will be investigated in future work. The re-parametrisation technique is based on a cross-sectional design approach. The duct test-case is intersected with several sections. These slices are later provided as an input to a lofting tool provided by the OCCT CAD library. The lofting tool generates a B-spline surface that approximates the input slices.⁷ The sections' parameters could be considered as design parameters of the fitting problem. Other possibility is to directly use the parameters of the B-spline surface produced by the lofting algorithm. Using the B-spline control point parameters for shape optimisation has been successfully demonstrated by Xu et al.^{9,10} Therefore, this kind of parametrisation is chosen here as well.

The final B-spline surface that approximates the optimised mesh can be retrieved by using the basic CAD features. To obtain it, the following steps are done: (i) extract the barycentric curve of the mesh, (ii) cut the mesh with m slices and distribute uniformly n points onto each slice, (iii) use this generated point cloud to construct a B-spline surface. Numbers m and n are chosen by the user and they differ from one test-case to another, i.e. there is no strict rule for choosing their values. Moreover, since only the S-part (highlighted with orange color in Fig. 2) is subject to modifications during the CAD-free optimisation workflow, we focus our analysis both for barycentric curve extraction and B-spline surface re-parametrisation on the S-part.

The barycentric curve is extracted using the OCCT features. The extraction process shown in Fig. 2 is the following:

1. Discretise the mesh with 80 sections equally distributed. Compute each section by using the *BRepAPI.Section* algorithm.
2. Compute the barycentric point for each slice by using the *BRepFeat* class.
3. Construct the barycentric curve by using *GeomAPI.PointsToBSpline* class. This is a class that approximates a B-spline curve passing through a set of points.

Once the barycentric curve is successfully extracted from the mesh data, the following step is to re-parametrise the optimised mesh with a B-spline surface. The re-parametrisation of the S-part is performed as follows:

1. Construct a number of mesh slices along the barycentric curve based on its curvature, as shown in Fig. 3. The curvature variation indicates the main areas where the mesh varies its shape.
2. Distribute uniformly a fixed number of points (60 in this case) onto the constructed slices. Use these points as control points of a B-spline curve that defines the new section.
3. Provide the newly generated set of sections to the OCCT class *BRepOffsetAPI.ThruSections* that approximates a B-spline surface.

It is important to note here that the approximation algorithm *BRepOffsetAPI.ThruSections* works efficiently when dealing with sections characterized by a similar or even better, equal number of control points. This is the reason why the slices constructed at the first step should not be provided to *BRepOffsetAPI.ThruSections*. Instead, we use their new versions with fixed number of control points constructed in the second step.

In this case the retrieved B-spline surface $S(u, v)$ (where (u, v) are the parameters defining the parametric space of the surface) is characterised by 60 control points in the u -direction \times 15 control points in the v -direction.

B. Back-to-CAD fitting algorithm with differentiated OCCT kernel

The previous subsection described a suitable design parametrisation for a duct topology such as the S-bend. Once this initial B-spline surface is constructed, the next step is to optimise its control points positions to best fit the initial surface. For this reason, we impose the following optimisation problem. All sample points

Figure 2. Left: S-bend test case, optimised mesh. Right: Barycentric curve evaluation, example with 8 slices; from left: slices extracted from the optimised mesh. Barycentric point computed per one slice. Barycentric point computed per every slice. Barycentric curve passing through the computed barycentric points.

Figure 3. Back-to-CAD fitting algorithm procedure. From left: extract a fixed number of slices (8 in this case) from the optimised mesh based on the barycentric curve's curvature. Uniform sampling of 60 points per slice. Compute the final B-spline surface. Optimised mesh vs computed B-spline surface.

are projected onto the retrieved B-spline surface, i.e. for each sample point we compute the parametric coordinates (u, v) within the patch that supports the sample point. This allows to define an objective function that is a sum of all the distances between a mesh point and its projection onto the B-spline surface:

$$\min_{x \in \mathbb{R}^{2700}} f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{15554} \|P_i(x) - T_i\|^2 \quad (1)$$

where i is the index of one of 15554 sampling points distributed onto the surface, $P_i(x)$ and T_i are the initial and target points respectively. Finally, this objective function is minimised by running a limited-memory BFGS optimisation algorithm where the design parameters x are the control points coordinates of the B-spline surface.

As described in the previous subsection, the total number of design parameters is 2700 (60 points in the u -direction \times 15 points in the v -direction \times 3 spatial dimensions). Despite of this large number of design parameters, the time required to compute the corresponding gradients is negligible (usually a couple seconds per iteration on an average desktop computer). This is due to a fact that we compute the gradients by using the reverse mode of AD,¹¹ which is highly efficient when having a large number of design parameters (independent variables) and much less objectives, i.e. single objective in our case – defined in Eq. (1). On the other hand, much more computational time is dedicated to the projection of the mesh points (15554 points) onto the B-spline surface, that is executed per every iteration of the optimisation.

Figure 4. From left: a) initial re-parametrised B-spline surface (red) vs optimised mesh (gold). b) Refitted B-spline surface (blue) vs optimised mesh (gold). c) Initial re-parametrised B-spline surface (red) vs refitted B-spline surface (blue) vs optimized mesh (gold).

The optimal B-spline surface shown in Fig. 4 results in a 90% reduction of the objective function value and it has been achieved in six primal/gradients evaluations. Therefore, the initial geometry constructed in the preprocessing step already closely matches the optimised mesh. To further reduce the objective function, one could consider increasing the number of slices distributed on the barycentric curve or increasing the number of B-spline surface control points to better match the mesh oscillations.

IV. Application 2: CAD-based Aerodynamic Shape Optimisation

An important ingredient of the aerodynamic shape optimisation is the parametrisation. Previous section describes how to use the re-parametrisation tool driven by the differentiated OCCT kernel to obtain rich parametric models. Once the rich parametric model is successfully defined, its aerodynamic performance can be improved using the gradient-based methods. In this section we explain how to incorporate parametric description into the gradient-based aerodynamic optimisation workflow. Moreover, we demonstrate such a workflow on a turbomachinery test-case.

A. CAD-based Shape Optimisation

To optimise a scalar cost function J which describes the aerodynamic performance of the system of interest, the optimisation problem can be stated as

$$\min_{\alpha} J(U(X(\alpha)), X(\alpha)), \quad (2)$$

$$R(U(X(\alpha)), X(\alpha)) = 0. \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) denotes the system of steady-state Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations, where the residual R is driven to zero. R is a function of the state variable U and the mesh coordinates X , both depending on the design parameters α . The objective function J could correspond to drag, lift, total pressure losses etc. Application of the chain rule to the system yields:

$$\frac{dJ}{d\alpha} = \left[\frac{\partial J}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial J}{\partial U} \frac{\partial U}{\partial X} \right] \frac{\partial X}{\partial \alpha}. \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the same operation for residuals gives:

$$\frac{dR}{d\alpha} = \left[\frac{\partial R}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial R}{\partial U} \frac{\partial U}{\partial X} \right] \frac{\partial X}{\partial \alpha} = 0, \quad (5)$$

and hence

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial X} = -\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial U}\right)^{-1} \frac{\partial R}{\partial X}. \quad (6)$$

Substitution of the last equation into (4) gives:

$$\frac{dJ}{d\alpha} = \left[\frac{\partial J}{\partial X} + v^T f\right] \frac{\partial X}{\partial \alpha}. \quad (7)$$

Here v represents the solution of adjoint equations:

$$\left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial U}\right)^T v = \left(\frac{\partial J}{\partial U}\right)^T, \quad (8)$$

where

$$f = -\frac{\partial R}{\partial X}. \quad (9)$$

With the adjoint approach, the cost of computing the sensitivities w.r.t. mesh coordinate X becomes independent of their size (contrary to direct approach defined in Eq. (6)).

After computing the solution of primal and adjoint equations (3), (8), one can map the obtained sensitivity w.r.t. the volume mesh nodes X on the design surface nodes X_S . Here we use the *inverse distance weighting* as the volume-surface deformation algorithm to calculate the sensitivity of the objective function J w.r.t. perturbation of design surface nodes X_S :

$$\frac{dJ}{d\alpha} = \frac{dJ}{dX_S} \frac{dX_S}{d\alpha}. \quad (10)$$

The first term in Eq. (10), the so-called called *CFD sensitivity*, corresponds to the sensitivity of the objective J w.r.t. perturbations in the surface grid point coordinates X_S . To calculate these derivatives we use our in-house discrete adjoint solver STAMPS.^{12,13} The second term, the so-called *CAD sensitivity*, represents the derivative of the surface grid points X_S with respect to the shape parameters, in our case the CAD model design parameters. This part is calculated by the algorithmically differentiated version of OCCT kernel.¹⁴

The gradient obtained in Eq. (10) is used in an iterative optimisation process to find optimal design parameters α by updating

$$\alpha^{(n+1)} = A(\alpha^{(n)}, \frac{dJ}{d\alpha}(\alpha^{(n)})), \quad (11)$$

where A represents an optimisation algorithm of choice.

B. TU Berlin Stator Test Case

The TUB TurboLab Stator is a realistic turbomachinery test-case proposed in a the optimisation workshop organised by the About Flow EU project on adjoint optimisation.¹⁵ The purpose of the stator is to turn the incoming flow of 42° whirl angle into an axial direction at the outlet, as shown in Fig. 5. Here, we consider minimisation of total pressure loss between the inlet and the outlet of the stator in a single-objective optimisation problem. The CAD-based method described here could be seamlessly extended for the multi-point and multi-objective optimisation problems also defined in the workshop (optimal design for 37°, 42° and 47° inlet whirl angle and with additional outlet angle objective).

The corresponding CAD geometry (STEP, IGES), manufacturing constraint specifications and further test-case details could be found on the workshop homepage.¹⁵

1. CFD set-up

The group at Queen Mary University of London is developing an open-source discrete-adjoint flow solver STAMPS (Source Transformed Adjoint Multi-Physics Solver).¹³ STAMPS uses a typical edge-based vertex-centred finite volume formulation to solve the flow equations on unstructured grids. The code is implemented in Fortran90, which enables application of source-transformation AD tool Tapenade for adjoint code development. This results in a very low memory footprint of the adjoint CFD run in comparison to operator-overloading AD techniques. The solver is used here to solve primal and adjoint flow equations and compute CFD sensitivities.

Figure 5. (Left) Top view of the TUB Stator blade with manufacturing constraints; (Right) BRep model of the TUB Stator

We used the stator CAD model to generate a computational grid (400k nodes) for the CFD simulation. At each optimisation step the computational mesh is synchronised with the updated CAD model via inverse distance mesh morphing technique implemented in STAMPS. No re-meshing is needed during optimisation process of the stator case.

C. TUB Stator in OCCT

The test case prescribes the following geometrical constraints on the blade that have to be satisfied during optimisation: (i) minimum radius of the leading and the trailing edge, (ii) minimum thickness of the blade (iii) minimum thickness near the hub and the shroud to accommodate the four mounting bolts and (iv) constant axial chord length. In the present work, the blade is re-parametrised in OCCT. The design parameters control the shape of the blade and their influence on the geometry is quantified by corresponding CAD derivatives. All constraints except the thickness constrains for the mounting bolts are explicitly embedded in the parametrisation. The ranges of corresponding CAD parameters could be provided to any optimiser workflow.

1. 2-D Profile Parametrisation

The proposed parametrisation is typically used for designing industrial blades. It starts by defining a 2-D profile. B-spline curves are used to represent the 2-D blade profiles, since they provide a rich and flexible space for the parametrisation.¹⁶ The 2-D blade profile is generated using a camber-line (shown in Fig. 6) represented by a B-spline curve and characterised by seven control points. Eight reference points ($P1, \dots, P8$) are distributed along the camber line using a cosine function as shown in Fig. 6. The cosine function is used to cluster points near the leading and trailing edge (LE and TE) of the camber-line. The control points for the suction and pressure side B-splines curves are generated as equidistant offsets of the reference points normal to the camber-line (Fig. 6). Finally, the suction and pressure side curves are smoothly joined using the specified radii of curvature satisfying G2 continuity.

The AB length (Fig. 6, eq. 12) in a B-spline curve of degree n is:

$$AB = \sqrt{\text{curvature} \cdot CH \cdot \frac{n-1}{n}} \quad (12)$$

where AB is the distance between control point A and B and CH is the distance of control point C from the AB line. Therefore, it is possible to impose the curvature in the point A .

This approach is applied to suction and pressure B-splines. In particular, the two curves have the same radius of curvature at the LE . This radius is controlled as design parameter of the optimisation. The same approach is also used for the trailing edge (TE) radius. Thus the G2 continuity is kept along all the section.

To summarise, the 2-D profile consists of 23 parameters of which, (i) 10 parameters control thickness (2 of them are the radii of TE and LE) and (ii) 13 parameters control the camber-line movement and therefore its angle, as shown in Fig. 7. This kind of parametrisation is suitable for aerodynamic optimisation

Figure 6. Left: Camber-line (blue) with corresponding control polygon (red) and uniform point distribution; Right: Construction of pressure/suction control points; Imposition of curvature (G2 continuity) at the LE

of turbomachinery components. First, the parameters have a full control over the section. Second, the guaranteed G2 continuity along all the sections allows the blade to smoothly drive the flow towards the outlet of the stator.

2. 3-D Parametrisation

The 3-D blade parametrisation is based on a cross-sectional design approach - the *lofting*. This approach takes n -slices (2-D profiles) as input and constructs final B-spline surface using an OCCT approximation tool. The slices are generated along a blade span defined as a B-spline curve, the *path-line*. Each 2-D profile parameter is characterised by a law of evolution along the *path-line*. The laws are defined as B-spline curves, consisting of 8 control points each. These control points are the design parameters of the optimisation. Their total number is 184 ($23 \cdot 8$). An example of the blade construction using seven slices is shown in Fig. 8.

D. Optimisation and Constraints

The limited memory BFGS algorithm with box constraints (L-BFGS-B) is used as optimiser. This allows us to impose bounding ranges for CAD parameters to comply with manufacturing constraints: e.g. minimum thickness, minimum leading/trailing edge radii.

Additionally, G2 continuity is imposed along all the sections based on the geometrical construction. The axial chord length is kept fixed: the axial-coordinate of the last camber-line control point is set to be equal to the axial-coordinate of the first control point plus the constant axial chord value.

The objective function to minimise is the pressure difference between the inlet and the outlet of the stator. After twenty iterations, the optimiser had modified the CAD parameters which resulted in an overall thinner blade and a leaning trailing edge at the mid-span. The optimised blade improves objective function by 7% and reduces the tip flow separation significantly (Fig. 9, Fig. 10).

Figure 7. Section parameters

Figure 8. Blade skeleton and TE law of evolution in the 3-D domain

Figure 9. (Left) Baseline and optimised blade results at the TE; (left) Difference in CAD geometries and mid-span profile comparison.

Figure 10. Tip streamlines for the initial (left) and the optimised TUB Stator (right)

V. Conclusions

A differentiated version of the open-source CAD library Open CASCADE Technology has been developed by applying Algorithmic Differentiation (AD) with the AD software tool ADOL-C.⁷ In this study we apply the differentiated OCCT to two gradient-based shape optimisation test-cases.

A first step in typical CAD-based optimisation workflows is to equip a given CAD shape with a suitable parametrisation, as in most cases there either is no parametrisation, or the parametrisation does not define a suitable design space for shape optimisation. The design variables of the parametrised shape need to then be adjusted to produce a best fit to the original baseline shape. Alternatively to being a pre-processing step, this fit can also be used as a 'back-to-CAD' step to approximate in CAD an optimised shape from a non-CAD shape optimisation method.

The application consists of two parts. First, a parametrisation is defined in CAD which can represent the baseline geometry and defines an appropriate design space. The presented example demonstrates a generic approach which is suitable for all non-manifold ducts. The parametrisation starts with fitting a curve through the duct barycentre and intersect the geometry with a number of slices along that curve. Each of the planar slices carries a spline curve defined by a set of control points. The final step of the parametrisation is to fit a B-spline surface through the curves on the slices by one of the lofting algorithms offered by OCCT CAD kernel.

As a second step, the algorithm formulates an objective function to measure the fit of the parametrised surface to the baseline geometry. In the presented case, the objective was the L2-norm of the distance in a large number of sampling points. Exploiting the availability of gradient information, gradient-based minimisation algorithms are then used to displace the control points of the B-spline surface such as to minimise the objective.

The second test-case is the shape optimisation of a parametrised CAD geometry. The presented case is the minimisation of the total pressure loss in a compressor stator blade. For this purpose, the differentiated OCCT is coupled with the discrete adjoint CFD solver STAMPS. The parametrisation consists of 184 design parameters and incorporates geometric constraints such as fixed radii for describing leading and trailing edge, while ensuring G2 continuity along all the blade. For all parameters, the CAD sensitivities computed with AD are verified by comparison against finite differences. The optimisation of the compressor blade using this fully-differentiated design chain results in a 7% reduction of the objective function. This improvement is mainly achieved due to the reduction of the tip flow separation that was verified with the baseline version of the stator.

The applications of the differentiated OCCT CAD kernel demonstrate that effective gradient-based optimisation is possible with complex CAD models being maintained inside the design loop.

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